

Tsallis Entropy and e_i/T power $-1/g$ Solution Instead of $\exp q$ Part 2

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In Part I, we noted how (1) uses the thermodynamic first law (with $dV=0$) $dU = T dS$ with $S = \sum_i g(p(e_i))$. (1) together with an a priori power law distribution $p(e_i) = C (e_i/T)^{-g}$ to show that the resulting entropy is of the Tsallis form: $-1/(1-q) \{\sum_i p(e_i)^q - 1\}$. Thus, (1) argues that a power law is also a solution of the Tsallis scenario. We note that (1) assumes that $U = \sum_i e_i p(e_i)$, while the usual Tsallis expectation value is $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q$.

Here we reexamine the approach of ((1)), especially the use of $dU = TdS$, which in thermodynamics is linked with quasistatic changes such that the system is always in equilibrium. The process of (1), however, holds T constant even as it integrates over $dp(e_i)$ to find S , but for an ideal case constant T means $dU = 0$, but in (1) it does not vanish. We suggest that this is a special process because it allows for $dp(e_i)$ to change without T changing. We suggest that this approach is really akin to a variational-stability one except for the fact that (1) uses a power law a priori and so does not impose a condition on p dF/dp (here p is unnormalized) as we did in Part I in a variational approach.

In other words, we suggest first that (1) is using a variational approach somehow masked as the first law of thermodynamics, and secondly that one does not need the distribution, here a power law, a priori, but that by imposing different conditions on p dF/dp (p unnormalized) one obtains various consistent probabilities. In particular, in a variational approach used in Part I we impose $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, but may use any moment of e_i , e.g. $\sum_i (probability \text{ for averaging}) e_i^n$, not simply the first moment used in $dU = TdS$.

Approach of (1) Revisited

The approach of (1) is based on finding an expression for entropy given an a priori probability distribution:

$$p(e_i) = C (e_i/T)^{-g} \quad ((1))$$

The entropy is found from the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dU = T dS \text{ with } dV = 0 \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{In particular, (1) writes: } S = \sum_i g(p(e_i)) \quad ((3))$$

Then, the differential is obtained by acting on $p(e_i)$, i.e. $dp(e_i)$. We suggest that one must be careful at this point because there are two kinds of $dp(e_i)$:

Case A: $p(e_i)$ changes in a quasi-static thermodynamical process such that $p(e_i)$ always represents the equilibrium probability. In particular, it may change because T (temperature)

changes without the functional form $\exp(-e_i/T)$ (Shannon-Maxwell-Boltzmann case) changing. This implies a change in $U(T)$.

Case B: In a maximization problem, one considers different functional forms of $p(e_i)$ and chooses one which is stationary to changes in the function, not in temperature T .

Thus, the use of the first law of thermodynamics implies Case A, while a variational approach, case B.

Given that (1) uses the first law of thermodynamics, it would seem that Case A is used, but that would imply that integrating $dU = T dS$, to find S (which is done) would mean that T changes, but it does not in the calculation of (1). In particular, T is held constant, but U changes. As a result, we suggest that the calculation of (1) is really akin to a variational approach. It differs from the variational approach we presented in Part I because (1) introduces a probability distribution a priori instead of imposing conditions on dg/dp .

We first examine explicitly the approach used in (1) and then show its link with the variational approach presented in Part I.

Using $dU = TdS$ with $dU = \sum_i e_i dp(e_i)$ $S = \sum_i g(p(e_i))$, (1) writes:

$$\sum_i (e_i - T dg/dp(e_i)) dp(e_i) = 0 \quad \text{define } \sum_i K_i dp(e_i) \quad ((4))$$

Here $p(e_i)$ is normalized and $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ ((5)).

An a priori power law distribution: $p(e_i) = C (e_i/T)^{-g}$ ((6)) is used.

Specifically, the authors of (1) allow e_i to run from e_0 to e_m and define $p_2(e_i) = e_0 p(e_i)$, $e_2 = e_i/e_0$ and write $p_2(e) = (e/T)^{-g} / B$.

$$\text{Then: } dg/dp (e_2(e_i)) = 1/(kT) \{ e_0 e_2(e_i) - K_i \} \quad ((7))$$

$$((6)) \text{ yields: } e_2(p_2(e_i)) = B^{-1/g} p_2(e_i)^{-1/g} \quad ((8))$$

K_i is a constant which may be found using $g(p_2(e_i))=0$ for $p_2(e_2(e_i))=0$ and $p_2(e_2(e_i))=1$.

As a result,

$$g(p_2(e_i)) = C_1 \{ -p_2(e_2(e_i)) + p_2(e_i)^{1-1/g} \} \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is readily integrated and is of a Tsallis form. A key point we make is that C_1 is a function of temperature and this is held constant. Normally, in a physical process linked with $dU = TdS$, T would change so it seems that (1) is really using a kind of variational process, but is then using

a priori a given distribution. We now try to compare ((7)) with the variational approach used in Part 1.

Comparison of (1) and the Variational Approach of Part I

We first note that in (1) only normalized probabilities are used. On the other hand, in the variational approach presented in Part I, unnormalized probabilities are utilized, but d/dp is also used. We suggest that this means the following:

If $p_1(e_i) = C(T) p(e_i)$, where p_1 is normalized and $p(e_i)$ is not then we consider a special change:

$dp_1(e_i)$ to be variational if $C(T)$ remains constant and only the functional form of $p(e_i)$ changes such that:

Sum over i $dp(e_i) = 0$. ((10)) In other words we focus on relative probabilities and changes to these.

The variational approach of Part I is to consider a function $F(p(e_i))$ (where $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized) such that:

$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((11)) where e_i/T is the relevant information. In the Shannon case, $F = \ln$.

Next, we consider any moment of e_i , e.g.:

Sum over i e_i power n probability used for averaging ((12))

In the Shannon case, $p(e_i)$ is used for averaging, while in the usual Tsallis case, $p(e_i)$ power q . In the case of (1), $p(e_i)$ is also used. Thus, the variational approach used in Part I is not restricted to the first moment contained in $dU = TdS$.

For simplicity, we consider the first moment: sum over i $p(e_i) e_i$, with $p(e_i)$ being used because it is used in (1). Here $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized. We then consider:

$p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ and take $d/dp(e_i) \rightarrow F(p(e_i)) + p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i)$ ((13))

Our key point is that $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ displays all of the relevant e_i/T information. Thus, $p(e_i)dF/dp(e_i)$ is either a constant 1 or constant $* e_i/T$, i.e. contains the same information. In the Kaniadakis case, matters are slightly more complicated.

We argued in Part I that using $p(e_i) dF/dp(e_i) = \text{constant} * e_i/T$ yields the power law of (1).

We now wish to show the similarity of the approach used in Part I and the variational approach just discussed. We examine ((4)) Sum over i $(e_i - T dg/dp_1(e_i)) dp_1(e_i) = 0$ and write:

$U = \sum_i e_i p_1(e_i) = \text{constant}$, (not the approach of (1)), but if $T = \text{constant}$ then this is fine. We do not consider $dU = TdS$.

$$\sum_i e_i dp_1(e_i) = 0$$

Now, the entropy we suggest in Part I is: $g = \sum_i p_1(e_i) F(p_1(e_i))$, where $p_1(e_i)$ is normalized.

$$\text{Then: } dg/dp_1 = F(p_1(e_i)) + p_1(e_i) dF/dp_1 \quad ((14))$$

$p_1 = C(T) p(e_i)$ where we consider $C(T)$ to be a constant.

Now $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, but here one has $F(p_1(e_i))$. The second term in ((14)) is:

$$C(T) p(e_i) dF/dp_1 \quad dp/dp_1$$

Let us consider the Shannon case as an example. Then $F(p_1) = \ln(p) + \ln(C(T))$

For ((14)) to sum to zero, one has $\ln(p) = -e_i/T$ so $\sum_i e_i dp_1(e_i) = 0$ so:

$$0 = \ln(C(T)) \sum_i p_1 + \sum_i p_1 dF/dp_1 \quad ((15))$$

Thus: $p_1 dF/dp_1 = \text{constant}$ is a solution. In other words, in the Shannon case, the approach of (1) is the same as the variational approach of Part I, except the variational approach of Part I allows one to solve for a probability distribution instead of introducing it a priori.

We consider the result of Part 1, for $p_1 dF/dp_1 = B e_i/T = -BF$, where B is a constant. We found that: $F = p_1^B - B$. Here p_1 is unnormalized.

Then: $F(p_1) = C(T) p_1^B - B$ $p_1^B - B = C p_1^B - B (-e_i/T)$ This sums to 0 because $\sum_i e_i dp_1(e_i) = 0$

We next consider $p_1 dF/dp_1 = -B C p_1^{B-1} p_1^B = \text{constant} * (-e_i/T)$ which also sums to 0

so the criterion of (1), namely that ((4)) sum to zero holds for dg/dp_1 (from (1)) = $p_1(e_i) dF(p_1)/dp_1$ where $p_1 dF/dp_1 = \text{constant} * e_i/T$ and $F(p_1(e_i)) = -e_i/T$.

In other words, the variational approach of Part I seems to be consistent with the approach of (1) except that the variational approach imposes conditions on $p_1 dF/dp_1$ which allow for one to find $p(e)$ distributions instead of introducing them a priori, as argued in Part I.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the approach of (1) is essentially a variational one even though $dU = T dS$ is used because an integral of dS is performed, but T (temperature does not change).

When we compare the method of (1) with the variational approach of Part I, we do not use $dU=TdS$. (For example, for an ideal gas, if T is held constant and $dV=0$, $dU = 0$, but that is not the case in (1).) We suggest rather that (1) is very similar to a variational approach introduced in Part I, except that (1) uses an a priori probability distribution whereas Part 1 introduces conditions on $p dF/dp$ (p unnormalized) to find probability distributions. As shown in Part I a certain condition, $p dF/dp = \text{constant} * (e_i/T)$ yields a power law probability.